

Physical Education Teachers in Spain

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Summary

This article analyzes the evolution in teaching physical education and curriculum in Spain since the first proposals for development that have received the Physical Education teachers with both the first specialized centre for teacher training, the key to its evolution since the mid-nineteenth century to General Management Act 1990 Education System entrusting the teaching of physical education teachers in primary education specialists in the field of Physical Education and which is developed through a Royal Decree of August 30, 1991, establishing the Master degree official in Physical Education and legislation for teacher education Physical education today.

Key words: education, legislation, education system, history, physical education, Spain

Evolution of Physical Education in Spain

The training of teachers of physical education has traditionally been towing laws declaring compulsory subject, but did not provide the necessary means for the training of teachers. This shortcoming of the Government in training teachers has harmed Physical Education. On many occasions it has had to resort to people without qualifications or with inadequate qualifications.

This work aims to determine roughly what has been the evolution of physical education in the Spanish legal framework.

It was not until the mid-nineteenth century for Physical Education (Gymnastics) began to appear in the curriculum. The Liberal government would create the Central School of Gymnastics Teacher in Madrid (1883–1892), passing a military-oriented physical education school based in France and Germany.

The most significant reform was triggered by the Physical Education Act of 1961 that recognized his teaching, looking for a modernization of future studies and approval of materials with the National Institute of Physical Education (INEF).

The following civilian centres would be the National School of Physical Education, "San Carlos", created in 1933 and the Academy of Physical Education of Catalonia, founded in 1936.

During the Franco Physical Education was classified in the institutions of the Movement, and managers of delivery were prepared at the National Academies Youth Front (ANJA).

From 1964–1965 the ANJA course is organized into three sections: Teachers, youth leaders and Physical Education. The latter section would be renamed College of Physical Education ANJA.

Physical Education Act of 1961 entrusted the National School "Julio Ruiz de Alda," the task of forming INEF female teachers, while recognizing the validity of all qualifications issued by the Central School of Physical Education of the Army, National Academy of controls "José Antonio" National School "Julio Ruiz de Alda, and Centers of the Ministry of National Education.

The INEF was created by Law 77/1961. Bet from the beginning by the specificity. His academic activity started in 1967 with a curriculum of four years.

The Royal Decree 790/1981 raised a new regulation INEF, where it could develop its own curriculum following the guidelines set by Order

of July 16, 1981, which provided the academic load and the compulsory subjects.

In the late eighties, the new curriculum being created INEF adapting to new social demands, evolving timidly towards other horizons.

The Royal Decree 1423/1992 of 27 November would authorize the Government to adapt the courses taken in INEF as provided in the University Reform Act of 1983.

Soon after, the Royal Decree 1670/1993 established the general guidelines of a new curriculum, based on which different institutions would develop their respective plans.

Physical Education has been present in greater or lesser extent, in nearly all the curricula of the curriculum of teacher training, but since 1989 when it begins to establish the specialty of Physical Education in Schools Teacher Training University GBS under the Law on Physical Culture and Sport 1980.

The decree has served to mitigate the heterogeneity of the curriculum between the different schools, but it has continued to exist and the criteria for the development of the curriculum have not always been optimal.

Physical Education in the Current Educational System

Curriculum is defined as the set of objectives, content, teaching methods and assessment criteria of each of the levels, stages, cycles, grades and conditions governing the education system teaching practice, therefore, to clarify terminology we can say that the concept of curriculum is the modern equivalent to what has traditionally been called programming and the definition of the Ministry, is marked for the whole country an official position about the educational curriculum in general and the PHYSICAL EDUCATION in particular, which is configured with the curricular elements that address the following questions:

1. Why teach: Objectives.
2. What to Teach: Content.
3. When teaching: Planning, sequencing of objectives and content, and courses cycles (timing).
4. Teaching: Activities. Methodology and Resources.
5. What, how and when to evaluate: Assessment.

Table 1. Outline of curriculum elements (Chinchilla and Zagalaz, 2002)

Level of detail	Responsible Agent	Function	Designation
First	Educational Administration through MEC and the Autonomous Communities with responsibility for education and their respective teams of experts.	Definition and development capabilities in the form of general behavior for an educational stage and each of its core curriculum.	General objectives of Stage. General objectives of area.
Second	Team teaching of a particular school (Faculty, Department, coordination of the cycle, etc.).	Contextualization of the objectives in the center and on the stage, and educational level cycle through the sources: Analysis of context. Prescriptive targets Other curricular materials	Objectives of the cycle. Level Objectives (On-PCC)
Third	Classroom Teachers	Contextualization of the objectives and realization of observable behaviors that students must achieve at the end of the study unit.	Learning objectives.

After reviewing the basic assumptions to develop the teaching action and outline the elements of the curriculum, we must make mention of the three levels of detail curriculum set by the legislature for the development of teaching-learning process (Zagalaz, 2002):

1. Curriculum Design Base (DCB). It is the first level of detail, corresponds to that set by the Ministry of Education and Science, which opted for an open curriculum model, ie on the minimum established by the Ministry itself for the entire national territory, be applied in successive concretions, by the appropriate

bodies, reaching the final contextualization of the curriculum into the classroom, adapting to the Autonomous Communities with responsibility for Education. It includes general objectives and cycle stage, curriculum areas and its overall objectives and final objectives. Should, therefore, what to teach, how to teach and how to assess, but the flexibility that allows teachers characterized develop their own classroom programming.

2. Curriculum Project Centre (PCC). Second level of specificity, issued by the school according to the DCB, collects basic goals and priorities, performance, methodology, contents, facilities, faculty, students and educational needs.

Classroom Scheduling (PA). Third level of detail, and the responsibility of teaching equipment and lecturer, is the planning of activities and tasks, model selection and preparation of teaching materials, which will result in appropriate programming, based on the elements of the curriculum.

Physical Education in Primary Education

According to Royal Decree 1513/2006, of December 7, laying down the curriculum for primary education teaching Physical Education will aim to help develop in students the skills that are in the following paragraphs.

1. Know and value their bodies and physical activity as a means of exploration and enjoyment of driving opportunities, relationships with others and as a resource for organizing leisure time.
2. Assess physical activity for welfare, showing a responsible attitude towards oneself and others and recognizing the effects of physical exercise, hygiene, food and postural habits on health.
3. Use their physical abilities, motor skills and their knowledge of the structure and functioning of the body to adapt the movement to the circumstances and conditions of each situation.
4. Purchase, choose and apply principles and rules engines to solve problems and take effective and autonomous practice of physical activities, sports and artistic expression.

5. Regular and dosing the effort, reaching a level of self-according to their possibilities and nature of the task.
6. Using the expressive resources of body and movement, aesthetic and creative manner, communicating feelings, emotions and ideas.
7. Participate in physical activities sharing projects, establishing relations of cooperation to achieve common goals, resolving conflicts through dialogue that may arise and avoid discrimination based on personal characteristics, gender, social and cultural rights.
8. To know and value the diversity of physical activities, games and sports as cultural elements, showing a critical attitude in the perspective of both participant and spectator.

Furthermore, as stated in the Royal Decree 1513/2006, of December 7, laying down the curriculum for Primary Education Physical Education will help to develop the following skills:

The area of physical education contributes significantly to the development of competition in the knowledge and interaction with the physical world through perception and interaction appropriate body, in motion or at rest in a determined area to improve their chances driving. It also contributes through knowledge, practice and assessment of physical activity being indispensable for preserving health. This area is key for children to acquire healthy habits and improving and maintaining physical condition accompanying them during the school and most importantly, throughout life.

In today's society progresses towards the optimization of mental and physical effort, it is essential to the practice of physical activity, but above all their learning and assessment as a means of psychophysical balance as a factor in preventing risks of inactivity and also as an alternative occupation of leisure time.

The characteristics of physical education, especially those concerning the environment that develops and class dynamics, make it conducive to social skills education, where educational intervention effect in this regard. Physical activities and in particular those that are made collectively are an effective means to facilitate interaction, integration and respect, while

contributing to the development of cooperation and solidarity.

Physical education helps students learn to live together, primarily in regard to the development and acceptance of rules for collective operation, with respect for personal autonomy, participation and appreciation of diversity. Activities aimed at the acquisition of motor skills require the ability to take on the differences and the opportunities and constraints and others. Compliance with the rules governing the games works in the acceptance code of conduct for interaction. Competitive physical activities can generate conflicts that need to be negotiated is based in dialogue as a means for resolution. Lastly, note that it helps to know the cultural wealth by practicing different games and dances.

This area contributes to some extent to the acquisition of cultural and artistic competition. The expression of ideas and feelings creatively contributes through the exploration and use of the possibilities and resources of the body and movement. The appreciation and understanding of cultural fact, and an appreciation of its diversity, it does through the recognition and appreciation of specific cultural human movement, such as sports, traditional games, activities and dance and expressive consideration as a heritage of peoples.

In another sense, the area provides an approach to sport as entertainment phenomenon through analysis and critical reflection about violence in sports or other situations contrary to human dignity that occur therein.

Physical Education helps the achievement of autonomy and initiative to the extent that calls upon students to make decisions with progressive autonomy in situations where they must express self-improvement, perseverance and positive attitude, also do, if given prominence the students in aspects of individual and collective organization of physical activities, sports and expressive.

The area contributes to competition learn how to learn by knowing oneself and one's own possibilities and shortcomings as a basis of motor learning to develop a varied repertoire to facilitate their transfer to more complex motor task.

This allows the establishment of achievable goals whose attainment generates confidence. At the same time, joint projects in group physical activities facilitate the acquisition of resources for cooperation.

On the other hand, this area works, from an early age, critical appraisal of the messages and stereotypes regarding the body, from the media and communication, which can damage the body image. From this perspective goes some way to competition on the processing of information and digital competition.

The area also contributes, like the rest of learning, the acquisition of linguistic communicative competence, offering a variety of communicative exchanges, the use of the rules that govern them and the specific vocabulary that the area provides.

According to Royal Decree 1513/2006, of December 7, laying down the curriculum for primary education content blocks are five Physical Education,

- Block 1, The body image and perception corresponds to the content to allow the development of perceptual-motor skills. It is particularly aimed at acquiring knowledge and control of one's body that is crucial both for the development of body image and for the subsequent acquisition of motor learning.
- In Block 2, motor skills together content that allow students to move effectively. They will be involved for both purchases related to the domain and motor control. Highlight the content that facilitate decision-making to adapt the movement to new situations.
- In Block 3, artistic and expressive physical activities are incorporated into the content intended to promote expression through the body and movement. Communication through body language has also been taken into account in this block.
- Block 4, Physical Activity and Health is made up of those skills necessary for physical activity is healthy. In addition, incorporate content for the acquisition of physical activity habits throughout life, as a source of comfort. The inclusion of a bloc that brings together content related to physical health from the perspective of physical activity is intended to emphasize the necessary acquisition of a

learning which obviously include all of the boxes across.

- Finally, Block 5, Games, Sports, presents material related to gambling and sports activities understood as cultural expressions of human movement.

Whether the game can be used as the methodological strategy also necessitates consideration as content for their anthropological and cultural value. On the other hand, the importance, in this type of content, gain interpersonal aspects of the proposal made remarkable here of attitudes directed towards solidarity, cooperation and respect for others.

In relation to the assessment and taking back to the 1513 decree Criteria evaluation, these are expressed per block specific content and educational cycle.

Physical Education in Secondary Education

According to Royal Decree 1631/2006 of 29 December, establishing the core curriculum for compulsory secondary education, physical education should contribute not only to build capacity and generate instrumental habits continued practice of physical activity, but also must link it to a scale of values, attitudes and norms, and knowledge of the effects on personal development, thus contributing to achieving the overall objectives of the stage.

The focus of this matter, has an inclusive and includes a multitude of functions: cognitive, expressive, communicative and well-being. First, the movement is one of the fundamental cognitive tools of the person, both to know themselves and to explore and organize its immediate surroundings.

Through the organization of their perceptions breasts-drive, become aware of one's body and the world around them, but also by the movement itself is improved motor skills in different situations and for different purposes and activities, enabling even show skills and overcome difficulties.

Furthermore, while the person uses his body and body movement to interact with others, not only in the game and sport, but in general all kinds of physical activities, promotes the art account of both instruments communication,

connection and expression. Likewise, through physical exercise contributes to the preservation and improvement of health and fitness, prevention of certain diseases and disorders and psychological balance, to the extent that people, through the same release tensions, leisure activities and enjoy their own movement and their effectiveness body. This is even more necessary given its role to compensate for environmental restrictions and the usual sedentary lifestyle of today's society. The physical education in this sense acts as a factor in prevention of first order.

The body and movement are, therefore, the basic axes that focus on educational activities in this area. It is, first, education of the body and movement in the direction of improving the physical and motor and hence the consolidation of healthy habits. Secondly, education throughout the body and movement to acquire skills and affective relationship, necessary for life in society.

The contents are organized around four major blocks: Block 1, physical and health condition, Block 2, games and sports, Block 3 and Block 4 Body language, Activities in the natural environment.

The teaching of physical education at this stage will aim to develop the following capabilities:

1. Knowing the characteristics that define a healthy physical activity and the beneficial effects that this has for the individual and collective health.
2. Rate and systematic practice of physical activities as a means of improving the health and quality of life.
3. Perform tasks aimed at increasing the chances of engine performance, improved physical fitness for health and improvement of the functions of adjustment, control and body control, adopting an attitude of self-demanding in its execution.
4. Meet and build healthy habits, basic techniques of breathing and relaxation as a means to reduce imbalances and relieve stresses caused in daily life and sports physical practice.

5. Planning activities to meet the demand in terms of physical abilities and specific skills from the initial assessment of the level.
6. Perform physical and sports activities in the natural environment with low environmental impact, contributing to its conservation.
7. Know and sports and recreational activities individual, collective and adversarial, applying the statutory technical and tactical fundamentals in game situations, with progressive autonomy in implementation.
8. Show skills and attitudes of respect, teamwork and sportsmanship in participation in activities, games and sports, regardless of cultural, social and skill.
9. Design practice and expressive activities with or without musical background, using the body as a means of communication and creative expression
10. Adopt a critical attitude towards the treatment of the body, physical activity and sport in a social context.

The Physical Education Teacher in Spain

To exercise physical education teaching in Spain (6–12 years primary education and secondary education 12 to 18 years) are necessary different university degrees.

Primary education: in order to practice the profession of physical education at the primary level is necessary to hold the degree in primary education (240 ECTS) may be issued only universities.

Primary Education is a compulsory stage of education, which courses between the six and twelve years of age, divided into three steps. The purpose of this stage is to contribute to personal and social development of school children through the teaching and learning in content area of artistic, scientific, ethical, linguistic, mathematical, and technological driving and action by appropriate mentoring.

Teachers must be able to participate actively in the design and development of innovative projects that contribute to the ongoing qualitative and quantitative improvement of the educational system.

The mandatory nature of this educational stage ensures the continued demand for

teachers for professional performance in public, private and private.

The projected increase in population will have to preschools families from other countries, and the future need to fill vacancies in the education sector due to the renovation of a large number of teachers (according to the Ministry of Education estimates that it will take more than 200,000 new teachers by 2015 to 2016 ongoing).

To teach physical education in primary school students should study the subjects that correspond to the respective "reference", in addition to the practicum in the teaching.

Secondary Education; the necessary qualifications to teach in secondary physical education in science is the degree of physical activity and sport, or sports science degree (240 ECTS), students must also complete a master in training faculty in the specialty of Physical Education (60 ECTS).

The Science Degree in Physical Education and Sport is the official university degree entitling the holder to work in areas like sports training, tourism and sports animation, corrective and remedial gymnastics, management companies and sports centers, rehabilitation functional effort and education. Linked to the Health Sciences, this course can gain skills in teaching methodologies, while the student sports activities related to training programs materials.

The number of teaching hours in primary is assigned 25 hours a week and 17 hours weekly secondary.

The retirement age in Spain is at 65.

Conclusions

Until the nineteenth century, do not begin to lay the foundations of Spanish education. From the end of that century, physical education began to be considered in the Spanish Educational System. During the twentieth century physical education is introduced with more or less interest in all levels of education, thus providing a definitive end of the century, thanks to the LOGSE and the demands and social acceptance it enjoys (Zagalaz, 2001) The LOE, in regard to physical education remains a sense of continuity and regressive because it reduces the number of hours devoted to physical education.

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